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Raúl Prebisch's influence on Contemporary Development Studies: A review of recent literature (2010-2021)

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Abstract

This research examines the influence of Prebisch's work on contemporary academic debates in development studies. To this end, a systematic literature review of studies published in the main development studies journals over the period 2010–2021 was conducted. A total of 139 articles were located and analyzed thematically. The articles were categorized according to their analytical approach, bibliographic citations, themes, treatment (anecdotal or deep), and misunderstandings and omissions of Prebisch's thought. With some exceptions, most of the articles allude to Prebisch in an anecdotal way, without delving into his thought and his extensive work. The results reveal a notable lack of knowledge about a pioneering author in development studies, especially regarding the final stage of his thought in which he tried to formulate a global theory of development. Despite this, Prebisch's thought connects with lines of research at the frontier of knowledge on the entrepreneurial state, ecologically unequal exchange, or post-extractivisms. A research and political agenda focused on his legacy requires placing at the center of the development debate issues such as the social use of surplus, the concentration of means of production, technological progress, industrialization, environmental challenges and, above all, the ethics of development.

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Introduction

The 75th anniversary of the United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC, or CEPAL in Spanish) marks a propitious moment for examining the influence of its most emblematic figure, Raúl Prebisch (b. 1901 Argentina; d. 1986 Chile). Although this author has been the subject of numerous studies, with some exceptions of a more biographical nature (Dosman 2010; Magariños 1991; Pollock et al. 2001), his work has mostly been disseminated in the Latin American context through articles published in the *CEPAL Review* (Gurrieri 1981; Ferrer 2010) or in seminars and monographs dedicated to his figure (Ocampo

2001).¹ More recently, Pérez Caldentey, Sunkel, and Torres (2012) carried out a historical review of the stages of his thought on Latin American development. As the authors mention, Prebisch constructed an original school of thought for the region, what he called the center-periphery approach or vision.²

According to some authors, from the very beginning, the approach headed by Prebisch following the public presentation in 1949 of his so-called *Havana Manifesto* or *ECLAC manifesto* (*The Economic Development of Latin America and Its Principal Problems* published in 1950 by ECLAC)³ distanced itself theoretically and methodologically from Eurocentric economic approaches, such as the Marxist (Paul Baran), neoclassical (Gottfried von Haberler, Jacob Viner, Gerald Baldwin), or heterodox developmentalist schools of thought (G. Myrdal or R. Nurkse).⁴ In the words of Streeten (1981), compared to the relevance of “Western” thinkers such as K. Gunnar Myrdal, Hans Singer, François Perroux, Ivan Illich, or Fritz Schumacher, Prebisch was the only one who could be classified as an “underdeveloped scholar.” During the years Prebisch was Executive Secretary of ECLAC (1950–1963),⁵ the organization grew and gained momentum and was enriched by the contributions of intellectuals such as Celso Furtado, Juan Noyola Vázquez, Jorge Ahumada, Aníbal Pinto, José Medina Echevarría, and Victor Urquidi, among many others. These authors, as Pérez Caldentey et al. (2012) explain, incorporated the historicist approach that

¹ For example, to commemorate the 100th anniversary of his birth in 2001, the *CEPAL Review* published a monographic issue in tribute to Raúl Prebisch that included articles by distinguished Latin American social scientists. Authors such as José Antonio Ocampo, David Pollock, Adolfo Gurrieri, Octavio Rodríguez, Mario Cimoli, or Edgar Dosman participated in the publication (see: <https://www.cepal.org/es/publicaciones/37880-revista-la-cepal-no75>).

² It is both noteworthy and illustrative that Prebisch first used this terminology as a young researcher to reflect the debate in Argentina on how Buenos Aires extracted wealth from a rural interior highly dependent on the capital (see Dosman 2010, 68).

³ Depending on who cites the work, it refers to the version of the Havana conference (1949), the publication in English a year later in UN documents (1950), the reprinted version published in the *Economic Bulletin for Latin America* (1964), or the re-publication by ECLAC on its 50th anniversary (1998).

⁴ While Prebisch’s contributions are often highlighted for their departure from Eurocentric views of development, it is important to acknowledge that he was not the only pioneer to do so. Arthur Lewis, who won a Nobel Prize, similarly emphasized the significant differences between developing countries and the specific constraints they faced. Both Lewis and Prebisch argued for the need to account for these asymmetries in economic analysis, laying the groundwork for the structuralist approach. It is important to note that Prebisch, unfortunately, referred very sparsely to other authors in his writings, which might have influenced interpretations of his theoretical positions.

⁵ Prebisch’s role in the recently created ECLAC (February 15, 1947) under Executive Secretary Martínez Cabañas began on March 10, 1949, after signing a four-month contract in Santiago, Chile. He was received with enthusiasm due to the unstable situation of the organization, which was undergoing a three-year trial period to determine if it could finally be consolidated and become a permanent institution of the United Nations. Following the Havana Conference in June 1949, Prebisch’s contract was renewed for another nine months, and it was not until July 26, 1950, shortly after the Montevideo conference and the good reception of the only major resolution passed at the meeting (the ten-point *Economic Decalogue*), that he was appointed Executive Secretary. See Dosman (2010, 263–264) for more details on Prebisch’s arrival at ECLAC and the inner history of its creation, with its stance against the US administration and the Economic and Social Council of the Organization of American States (OAS). For an exhaustive description of this period, see also the chapters of Celso Furtado’s autobiography dedicated to his work at ECLAC (Furtado 1988).

became the cornerstone of ECLAC's analysis: the historical-structural method (Bielschowsky 2010).⁶ The thinking of Prebisch and ECLAC drew upon the international trade relations of Latin American countries and emphasized the reproduction of wage, technological, and power disparities between the center and the periphery (Prebisch 1981).

This article aims to analyze the influence of Prebisch's work on the contemporary academic debate in development studies. To this end, I do not take account of the research on his legacy but focus my search exclusively on academic articles published in the period 2010–2021 in the main "Development Studies" journals according with the Journals Citation Report (JCR) ranking of Web of Science 2020 prepared by the Institute for Scientific Information (ISI). The choice of this period is due to both the interest in having a current snapshot of Prebisch's thought and because it is the period with the highest frequency of citations to his work in the Web of Science database since 1961 (see Appendix 1); the year when the first reference to his work is recorded. This period not only captures how contemporary scholars engage with Prebisch's contributions but also reflects an evolving understanding of his theories in the context of modern development challenges. Addressing these contemporary interpretations helps to counteract any simplistic or caricatured views of his contributions. After applying the inclusion criteria, I have compiled a total of 139 articles and grouped them according to their main themes, analytical approach, citations and references to Prebisch, treatment of Prebisch's work (anecdotal or original), and relevant lessons for addressing the future of development studies. I have also identified arguments in Prebisch's thought that have not been addressed in the selected articles.

To achieve the above objectives, following the introduction, the next section explains the methodology used in the systematic literature review and the thematic analysis. The second section (results) provides a descriptive analysis of the articles that allude to Raúl Prebisch in a marginal and anecdotal way and groups his contributions into two broad themes: (1) the Prebisch–Singer hypothesis and unequal trade exchange; and (2) industrialization experiences and the idea of import substitution. Finally, the third section presents the main conclusions and offers new insights

⁶ While Prebisch is often seen as the primary figure behind the ideas of ECLAC, it is essential to recognize that the school's contributions extend beyond his work, primarily regarding the treatment of specific economic phenomena. An example is the case of inflation theory, in whose debates, figures such as Juan Noyola Vázquez played a critical role in shaping structuralist thought (Paz 2021). Understanding these differences is crucial for a comprehensive view of the school's legacy. As Arndt (1985) noted, the term 'structuralism' first came into use in relation to these explanations of inflation, rather than in the early writings about development. For the evolution of ECLAC thought, see Barcena et al., (2022), Beteta and Moreno-Brid (2012), Bielschowsky (1998), and Gurrieri (1982). For the roots of structuralist development theory through Prebisch and ECLAC, see Calcagno (2021).

for the future Agenda for Sustainable Development in the framework of Prebisch’s main contributions.

1. Search method, description of the selected bibliography, and thematic analysis

Raúl Prebisch’s thought has been disseminated through a variety of channels and sources for knowledge transfer, including books, chapters, papers, reports, media information, and training programs, among others. In this paper, I restrict the analysis solely to academic journals and specifically to articles published in journals considered to have the highest international impact factor in the discipline of “Development Studies” according to JCR. A total of 43 journals were selected (see Table 1): all 42 indexed in the “Planning and Development” category, along with 1 journal from the “Economics” category, which was selected for its relevance in the field of development studies.⁷ JCR is the world’s leading multidisciplinary database for evaluating the impact of academic journals. Madrueño and Tezanos (2018) used a similar strategy to analyze the influence of four of the most influential academic journals (*World Development*, *Development and Change*, *Third World Quarterly*, and *European Journal of Development Research*) in shaping the development discourse.

Table 1. Selected journals and type of articles that cite Prebisch (2010–2021)⁸

Journals ranked by JCR impact factor (2020)	Final selection	Type 1 (48%)	Type 2 (19%)	Type 3 (33%)
1. <i>Long Range Planning</i>	0	0	0	0
2. <i>Cambridge Journal of Regions Economy and Society</i>	4	1	2	1
3. <i>Journal of Peasant Studies</i>	0	0	0	0
4. <i>Sustainable Development</i>	0	0	0	0
5. <i>Habitat international</i>	0	0	0	0
6. <i>World Development</i>	14	4 (1 ^β)	0	10 (2 ^β)
7. <i>Entrepreneurship and Regional Development</i>	0	0	0	0
8. <i>World Bank Research Observer</i>	1	1	0	0
9. <i>Climate and Development</i>	0	0	0	0
10. <i>Information Technology for Development</i>	0	0	0	0

⁷ This methodological choice to understand the impact of Prebisch in development economics, while providing valuable insights, has some clear biases. Although impact factors and academic rankings are standard methods that are spreading globally from the Anglo-Saxon sphere, they are purely quantitative measures that limit other forms of knowledge dissemination, such as books, book chapters or grey literature, which includes project reports, technical material, and academic papers not disseminated through conventional publishing channels.

⁸ The journals are listed in the order of their ranking in the JCR’s ‘Development and Planning’ category, where ‘Long Range Planning’ ranks highest in impact, and ‘IDS Bulletin-Institute of Development Studies’ ranks lowest.

11. <i>Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning</i>	0	0	0	0
12. <i>Development and Change</i>	27 (1*)	23 (5 ^β)	0	4
13. <i>Society & Natural Resources</i>	0	0	0	0
14. <i>Social Policy & Administration</i>	0	0	0	0
15. <i>Journal of Environmental Planning and Management</i>	0	0	0	0
16. <i>Journal of Agrarian Change</i>	3 (2*)	3	0	0
17. <i>Journal of Economic Policy Reform</i>	9	3	2	4
18. <i>Housing Policy Debate</i>	0	0	0	0
19. <i>Third World Quarterly</i>	20	12 (1 ^β)	7	1
20. <i>European Journal of Development Research</i>	8	2	4 (1 ^β)	2
21. <i>Journal of Development Studies</i>	6 (1*)	3	2	1
22. <i>Growth and Change</i>	1	0	1	0
23. <i>World Bank Economic Review</i>	1	0	0	1
24. <i>Studies in Comparative International Development</i>	3	3	0	0
25. <i>Journal of Environment & Development</i>	0	0	0	0
26. <i>African Development Review</i>	4	0	0	4
27. <i>Journal of Human Development and Capabilities</i>	0	0	0	0
28. <i>International Development Planning Review</i>	0	0	0	0
29. <i>Journal of International Development</i>	5	0	1	4
30. <i>Economic Development and Cultural Change</i>	1*	1	0	0
31. <i>Economic Development Quarterly</i>	1*	1	0	0
32. <i>Development Policy Review</i>	3	2	0	1
33. <i>Canadian Journal of Development Studies</i>	8	4	4 (1 ^β)	0
34. <i>Public Administration and Development</i>	1*	1	0	0
35. <i>Development Southern Africa</i>	3	0	3	0
36. <i>Journal of South Asian Development</i>	1	0	0	1 (1 ^β)
37. <i>Review of Development Economics</i>	8	0	0	8
38. <i>Progress in Development Studies</i>	2	2	0	0
39. <i>Community Development Journal</i>	0	0	0	0
40. <i>Journal of Development Effectiveness</i>	0	0	0	0
41. <i>Developing Economies</i>	0	0	0	0
42. <i>IDS Bulletin-Institute of Development Studies</i>	1	1	0	0
** <i>Journal of Development Economics</i>	4	0	0	4 (4 ^β)
	139	67 (7 ^β)	26 (2 ^β)	46 (7 ^β)

*Book Reviews (included in Type 1).

^βArticles that analyze Prebisch's work in depth and in an original way. There are a total of 16 articles of this type (12% of all articles selected). I will note them with the same symbol when citing them in the following sections. In

percentage terms, these articles represent 11.7%, 7.6%, and 15% of the articles included in types 1, 2, and 3, respectively.

**Journal indexed in the “Economics” and not in the “Planning and Development” category.

The search for articles that cite Raúl Prebisch was carried out on the website of each journal. Additionally, to control for duplicities and detect possible errors, the Scopus bibliographic database was used. Compared to other databases such as the Web of Science, Scopus allows exhaustive searches of citations and has greater coverage of texts in the social sciences and humanities. The selected articles had to meet the following three inclusion criteria: (a) journal articles that mention Raúl Prebisch in the main text or in the references⁹; (b) articles published in journals ranked in JCR’s “Planning and Development” subject category and in the *Journal of Development Economics* (ranked in the “Economics” subject category); and (c) articles published in the period 2010–2021. After applying these search criteria, a total of 139 articles were selected (see Figure 1). Figure 1 was created using the search procedure described in the PRISMA protocol (Moher et al. 2009). The process concluded after downloading the data in June–August 2022 and the subsequent analysis of the information.

Figure 1. Flow diagram

⁹To avoid the possible omission of some references, we have included in the searches the titles of two documents written by Prebisch (1950 1964) referring to the institution that commissioned them when citing the ECLAC manifesto and Karshenas conference “Towards a New Trade Policy for Development.” In both cases, they have been counted as citations to Prebisch.

As can be seen in the flow chart, a total of 549 publications were identified in the 43 journals searched. Of these publications, 139 correspond to the period 2010–2021. Because Scopus does not initially allow filtering searches by journal, the initial results of this search are more numerous. In Scopus, 4593 publications cite Prebisch over the period 1960 to 2022 (2705 articles, 801 book chapters, 668 books, 302 reviews, 55 conference papers, 42 editorials, 16 notes).¹⁰ Of these, 1748 correspond to articles published over the period 2010–2021, 145 of which were published exclusively in the 43 selected journals. When comparing the results with those obtained from the journals' websites to eliminate duplications, a total of 139 articles that cite Prebisch were obtained for the period 2010–2021 (see Appendix 2).¹¹ In reading and processing the articles I have also eliminated those which included inappropriate references to Prebisch. For example, the work by Pipkin (2017) cites an article by Alice H. Amsden (2004) with a title where Raúl Prebisch's name appears. Articles with indirect citations to Prebisch have not been excluded. For example, in Toye (2014), who refers to Prebisch's work citing Dosman's (2010).

These 139 articles allude to Prebisch's work in two ways to achieve their objectives: 122 mention the author in an anecdotal manner (87.8% of the total) and 16 attach considerable weight to his work to elaborate their arguments (these articles are marked with a 'β' in superscript in Table 1 and when cited in the following sections). Regarding the analytical approach, I identify three approaches used in the articles to achieve their research objectives: theoretical-discursive (67, type 1 in Table 1); theoretical-discursive with descriptive data analysis (26, type 2 in Table 1); and empirical (46, type 3 in Table 1).

Following the categorization of the 139 articles, I thematically analyzed (Braun and Clarke 2006, 2012) the 16 articles that explore Prebisch's work in greatest depth and the passages that refer to his work in an additional 123 articles. To this end, I followed the six-stage procedure developed

¹⁰ See Appendix 1 for descriptive information on the 4593 references to Prebisch's work in Scopus from 1961 to 2021.

¹¹ To avoid including such extensive bibliographical references in the manuscript, I have relegated the 139 articles selected for review to Appendix 2 (i.e., final references selected in each journal) and ordered them according to the journal in which they are published.

by Braun and Clarke (2006) to inductively code the texts in line with the research objectives. In Braun and Clarke's (2006) original protocol the person conducting the analysis must focus on the discourses (in my case written) and present only the identified themes as results. In this paper I have chosen to present the main themes and discuss them in the light of Prebisch's work through a critical analysis of the selected articles. This might seem to be at odds with the method of presenting the results, but it is better suited to the objectives of the present article and limitations of space of an academic article.

2. Results and discussion

Following the methodological decisions outlined in the previous section, in what follows I identify and discuss the main results of the research.

2.1. Raúl Prebisch: referenced and cited, but little explored

As I mentioned in the first section, most of the articles analyzed (122; 87.8%) do not go into depth on Prebisch's ideas and cite him (1949, 1959) for general assumptions of an abstract nature, such as how international economic integration fosters structural inequalities between developing and developed countries (Horner et al. 2018; Jarrín-V 2021), how the dynamics of surplus value transfer and technological gaps across countries lead to unequal terms of trade through international trade relations (Naudé 2011; Storm 2015), or the debate on trade gaps between Prebisch's ideas and the theses of Ricardo's comparative advantage theory (Nabar-Bhaduri 2018). It is also common to find repeated citations to the Prebisch–Singer thesis to point out the drawbacks of specializing in raw materials and agricultural goods (Mann and Iazzolino, 2021; Sneyd 2014). These citations are closely related to those that mention Prebisch as a reference in the field of industrialization and import substitution industrialization strategies in countries of the Global South (Mazzucato and Penna 2016; Storm, 2017; Perez-Aleman and Chaves Alves 2017).

Many other articles mention Prebisch only as a leading figure in the international development circle of the 1950s and 1960s. It is common to find him cited alongside two groups of authors. On the one hand, Prebisch is associated with development pioneers such as Walt W. Rostow, Arthur Lewis, Albert O. Hirschman, Nicolas Kaldor, or Gunnar Myrdal.¹²This is the case of Andreoni and Chang (2017) or Romero and Gramkow (2021), who mention that the common denominator

¹² Irwin's article (2021^β) shows clear differences in the theoretical and policy proposals of Prebisch and some of his contemporaries, such as Gunnar Myrdal, Ragnar Nurkse, or Albert O. Hirschman.

of these authors is that they argued for the crucial role of industrialization or structural change towards modern sectors for sustained economic growth in very different ways. On the other hand, Prebisch also appears recurrently together with the Latin American economists of the 1960s such as Celso Furtado, Osvaldo Sunkel, or Fernando Henrique Cardoso. More specifically, Orihuela (2013) highlights his connection with the ideas of the Chilean economist Jorge Ahumada on Chile's inability to do away with the "structural forces" that made inflation a chronic problem in the country. From a perspective more focused on his person, other articles cite Prebisch as the most representative figure of ECLAC, the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), and structuralist theory (Morvaridi and Hughes 2018; Saad Filho and Tomkinson 2017).

As regards articles that employ analytical approaches to achieve their research objectives, 48% (67) of those analyzed are discursive-theoretical, 18.7% (26) of the articles are discursive-theoretical with descriptive data analyses and 33% (46) are empirical. The first two types include topics ranging from reviews on problematic issues such as industrialization (Andreoni and Chang 2017; Storm 2017), globalization (Horner et al. 2018), the Sustainable Development Goals (Fukuda-Parr and Muchhala 2020), the new gold standard in economics (Kvangraven 2020^b), or the role of entrepreneurship in development (Naudé 2011) to essays on prominent figures in the field of development studies such as Theotônio Dos Santos (Kay 2020^b) or Ajit Singh (Saith 2018). There are also specific investigations of policy proposals by international organizations such as Karshenas (2016^b), Toye (2014^b), and Rada (2014) on the origins, evolution, and achievements of the UNCTAD. The eminently empirical articles include both econometric works using time series or panel data for numerous countries in the long run, as well as more qualitative approaches and case studies. Among the econometric works, there are multiple investigations of commodity price fluctuations and their macroeconomic consequences in different regions or countries (Byrne et al. 2013^b, Chuku et al. 2018, Harvey et al. 2017^b; Winkelried, 2018^b).

From the number of publications that refer to Prebisch in this period and the journals considered, it could be interpreted that his work holds a prominent place in development studies.¹³ However, upon closer examination, two observations suggest a different perspective. Notably, among the 43 journals reviewed, 41% (18) do not contain any references to the author. . If we add those with a single citation, the figure increases to 57% (25 journals). On the other hand, 65% of the citations appear in just six journals, three of which contain 43% of all references to Prebisch (*World*

¹³ Also, as shown in Appendix 1, citations to Prebisch increased considerably over the period 2008–2010 regardless of the source (articles, book chapters, books, etc.).

Development, Development and Change, and *Third World Quarterly*).¹⁴ The second observation has to do with the cited works of Raúl Prebisch. Despite the author's vast oeuvre, of the 139 articles that make reference to him, none of his works are cited in 20% (29) and merely name him anecdotally (Block 2014; Thakur 2016; Chandrasekhar 2015; Fukuda-Parr and Muchhala 2020; Nem Singh and Ovadia 2018; Sneyd 2014). Other works allude to his thought via another author's research. Interestingly, this occurs in 2 of the 16 articles for which Prebisch's work is central. Toye (2014^β), for example, cites him indirectly 21 times from Dosman's (2010) biography of Prebisch. Karshenas (2016^β) names him 11 times throughout the article, but only cites the 1964 UNCTAD report on behalf of the institution and mentions no other works by Prebisch. Likewise, Fischer (2015), despite the importance he attaches to Prebisch's ideas in his article, cites him only from the ECLAC manifesto or when alluding to Polanyi Levitt (2005).

As regards the 110 articles that do cite works by Prebisch in the bibliographic references, we find 129 citations to a total of 16 works, which represent an extremely small portion of his written legacy. As can be seen in Table 2, 78.2% of the total citations to Prebisch are to the *Havana Manifesto* (Prebisch 1950) or the article "Commercial Policy in the Underdeveloped Countries" published in the *American Economic Review* nine years later (Prebisch 1959). Considering that Prebisch's work includes at least 446 sources (among them presentations, conferences, dialogues, interventions, declarations, speeches, lectures, reports, studies, commentaries, correspondence, memoranda, notes, forewords, articles, book chapters, and books), the citations to Prebisch in the articles represent an insignificant part of his academic production (3.6%).¹⁵

Table 2. Raúl Prebisch's cited works

Prebisch's "cited" works	Articles that cite Prebisch
- <i>Havana Manifesto</i> (1950)	79(61%)
- <i>American Economic Review</i> (1959)	22 (17%)
- UNCTAD (1964)	11 (8.6%)
- <i>Capitalismo periférico</i> (1981)	3 (2.3%)
- Others (12 publications)	17(13.1%)
Total	129

¹⁴ These three journals are among the four Madrueño and Tezanos (2018) chose to analyze the contemporary development discourse. The fourth journal (*The European Journal of Development Research*) cites Prebisch eight times. *The European Journal of Development Research*, the *Canadian Journal of Development Studies* and the *Review of Development Economics* contain the same number of citations to Prebisch.

¹⁵ A chronological bibliography with the 446 sources can be found in a book prepared jointly by the CEPAL/ILPES Library as a tribute to his figure one year after his death (CEPAL 1987, 41–146).

2.2. Raúl Prebisch: deep debates and future lines of research

In what follows, I present the main topics addressed in the articles that go beyond the anecdotal when citing the author. I also identify lines of research of interest for the current development agenda.

The first theme corresponds to mostly econometric quantitative analyses that provide new evidence to determine whether the Prebisch–Singer thesis (Prebisch 1950; Singer 1949, 1950) has held true in the long term and how or for what contexts (Chakraborty 2012^β).¹⁶ According to this thesis, there is a downward trend in prices of primary commodities relative to those of manufactured products, what is known as primary commodity terms of trade. These discoveries, theorized under Prebisch’s center-periphery approach, were widely disseminated in the *Havana Manifesto*. Again, David Ricardo’s comparative-advantage theory implies that countries do better by specializing as opposed to diversifying exports. For the last 70 years, the issue of long-term declining prices has given rise to an immense body of literature. These studies incorporate new indicators, data bases (Harvey et al. 2010), measurement techniques (Winkelried 2018^β; Ghoshray 2011^β; Harvey et al. 2017^β), variables (interest rates, export specializations, Daruich et al. 2019^β), a variety of products (oil prices, non-oil commodities prices, tropical and non-tropical agriculture, and metals), super-cycles (Erten and Ocampo 2013^β), and regions or countries (Cyphe 2010^β; Farooki 2011^β)

The results of the Prebisch–Singer thesis during its theorization and early empirical developments led to a policy shift driven by ECLAC towards international initiatives to escape from the “primary products curse.” The most prominent example in the articles analyzed refers to Prebisch’s thesis on industrial policy design based on import substitution industrialization (ISI). The central countries, the major beneficiaries of the exchange system, orient their production towards manufacturing goods with advanced technology, which gives them greater capacity to absorb labor and obtain surpluses from the production process. In contrast, by focusing on the export of primary goods and raw materials, the peripheral countries not only depend on the technology of the central

¹⁶ The Prebisch–Singer thesis was not formulated in a co-authored publication but is known as such due to the important role of both figures in its development. In a report prepared for the UN Sub-Commission on Economic Development (*Post-war Price Relations Between Under-developed and Industrialized Countries*, later renamed *Relative Prices of Exports and Imports of Under-Developed Countries*; United Nations, 1949), Singer employed statistics from the second half of the 19th century to the eve of World War II to demonstrate a decline in the real terms of trade of developing countries. These findings provided long-term empirical evidence of the idea that Prebisch had been developing theoretically since his publication *La moneda y el ritmo de la actividad económica* (1943): the downward trend in prices of raw materials in relation to prices of manufactured products.

countries, but also have a very limited capacity to absorb the labor force (Prebisch 1983). If technology were to penetrate the primary sector and increase its productivity, this would create pockets of unemployed that would be untenable for their national economic structures. If, on the other hand, they opt to industrialize in order to substitute imports, they will be at a clear disadvantage with respect to the centers, due, among other reasons, to the scarcity of technology.¹⁷ One option to overcome these difficulties, while continuing with a primary export model, would be to protect the domestic industry to boost its competitiveness. However, if the domestic market is not large enough to absorb the manufacturing supply, it will continue to fall into a vicious cycle. Geenen (2019) and Radley (2020) ground these ideas in Prebisch's contributions to the implantation of extractive industries in local territories, the so-called "enclave thesis."¹⁸ These investigations are linked to the contemporary literature on extractivism, neo-extractivism, and *extrahección*; a Spanish term coined by Gudynas to refer to the violent appropriation of natural resources (Andrade 2022; Gudynas 2021; Veltmeyer and Ezquerro-Cañete 2023).

Analyses of the Prebisch–Singer thesis also extend to another line of research that focuses on the terms of unequal ecological exchange between centers and peripheries (Pérez-Rincón 2006). Even though these debates do not appear in the development journals analyzed here, Prebisch's ideas clearly intersect with issues of equity and sustainability (ECLAC 2014; Martínez Alier 2013; Domínguez et al. 2019).¹⁹ Rival et al. (2015) brought to light Prebisch's imprint on contemporary ECLAC publications that argue for a broad social and political consensus to achieve structural changes that enhance competitiveness and equity based on environmental sustainability. In this field, Prebisch is still "alive," and his original contributions are opening a fruitful line of research that connects with ecological economics, degrowth, and post-capitalist discussions (Martínez-Alier 2012). There are also novel proposals using a quantitative approach that provide evidence of the very negative implications of the Global South's commercial patterns of specialization (1900–

¹⁷ Other reasons for the problems of the ISI strategies included the intensive import requirements in capital goods that would exacerbate the tendency of foreign exchange gaps. ISI strategies aimed to begin with the production of final goods and move gradually toward intermediate goods and capital goods.

¹⁸ The "enclave thesis" refers to the process by which foreign companies insert themselves into the national productive fabric and create highly productive enclaves that are globally connected with exports but impermeable to the local market except in very favorable stages. These enclaves produce social asymmetries and productive gaps; in short, a structural heterogeneity that deepens labor market segmentation and increases income, class, and territorial inequalities in productivity. Radley's (2020) sole case study of a gold mine in the Democratic Republic of Congo is representative of a process of foreign-controlled gold sector (re)industrialization underway across a group of 20 low-income African countries. His findings confirm rather than invalidate the original enclave thesis, observing that corporate outsourcing has done little to stimulate broader industrialization while facilitating the arrival and expansion of foreign firm subsidiaries.

¹⁹ Prebisch only briefly addressed this issue in the final pages of his article "Biosphere and development" (1980). He covered the ecological issue somewhat more extensively in his book, Prebisch (1981).

2016) not only in terms of economic development, but also in terms of environmental problems (Infante-Amate et al. 2020, 2022). These discussions are related to others on bioregions, extractivism, and energy colonialism that show how the pattern of agricultural specialization in countries of the South is increasing the agricultural area to supply the Global North (Sánchez Contreras and Matarán 2023).²⁰

Finally, another topic for which Prebisch is cited in-depth is the history of ideas of theoretical approaches that are largely absent in discussions and official agendas on development, such as Latin American structuralism, the dependency theory, or the world system theory. He is also cited in works on authors of reference in pioneering discussions on development, such as Samir Amin (Domínguez 2019; Kvangraven 2021^β) or Theotônio Dos Santos (Domínguez 2018; Kay 2020), as well as in works on leading economic thinkers such as Gunnar Myrdal, Arthur Lewis, Albert O. Hirschman, or Ragnar Nurkse (Irwin 2021^β) and lesser-known authors outside conventional circles such as Celso Furtado, Ander Gunder Frank, or José Carlos Mariátegui. As for studies that examine the history of Prebisch's ideas, the review essay by Vernengo (2013^β) reveals several lines that are worth exploring, such as the influence of cultural and political circles (i.e., the Bunge brothers, his international connections, etc.), Prebisch's political collaborations with the Argentine dictatorships, or the origins of the Prebisch–Singer thesis (or vice versa).

2.3. Raúl Prebisch: errors and omissions

A first type of errors and omissions in some of the literature analyzed has to do with Prebisch's influences and theoretical ascriptions. He is often incorrectly labeled, alongside authors such as Fernando Henrique Cardoso, Enzo Faletto, or Immanuel Wallerstein, as a Marxian political economist, particularly in the form of dependency or the world systems theory. This is the case of Horner et al. (2018), Lim and Prakash (2017), or Fukuda-Parr and Muchhala (2020). It is also true of Akbulut et al. (2015), who includes Prebisch (together with Paul Baran and Paul Sweezy) among the 1960s Marxist-inspired critics of mainstream development economics. Despite these theoretical assumptions, most of the literature on Prebisch's intellectual influences alludes to his transition from conventional to Keynesian premises,²¹ until the development of a genuine

²⁰ The term *bioregion* became popular following the seminal work of Thayer (2003, 3) and refers to “a unique region definable by natural (rather than political) boundaries with a geographic, climatic, hydrological, and ecological character capable of supporting unique human and nonhuman living communities.”

²¹ Prebisch wrote a widely publicized introduction (1947) and multiple texts on Keynes (see the collection of his complete works, 1991, 1993). For the influence of Keynes on Prebisch, see Mallorquin (2017), Sunna (2014), or Pérez Caldentey and Vernengo (2015).

structuralist approach to economics. According to Prebisch himself (1983), his career evolved over five stages.²²

Throughout these stages of his career, Prebisch is known for having gradually distanced himself from neoclassical economics, and although his work inspired structuralist developments in dependency theory (Celso Furtado, Oswaldo Sunkel, Fernando H. Cardoso), he eschewed revolutionary Marxist positions, such as those of André Gunder Frank. Drawing from a work on Theotônio Dos Santos, Kay (2020^b) explores the discrepancies between Prebisch's position and dependency theory. While dependency theory developed a critique of unequal terms of trade grounded in Marxist labor theory, Prebisch focused on how surplus labor in the periphery steadily deteriorates the terms of trade, leading to continuous declines in productivity and wages. This is in line with what Arthur Lewis referred to in his seminal work on the unlimited supply of labor (1954). Although in his final writings Prebisch continued to exhibit a clear reformist spirit without a strong criticism of imperialism, he theorized a synthesis between socialism and economic liberalism to transform the system based on the social use of surplus (Prebisch 1981).²³

In yet another series of misunderstandings, we find continuous references to Prebisch as a champion of state intervention in the economy, the shift away from the export of primary products, import substitution industrialization, and industrial policy in Latin America in the 1960s and 1970s. Prebisch's arguments on these issues, as can be seen in most of his works (1949, 1950, 1954, 1964, 1981), are full of nuances and a wealth of casuistry that deserve clarification. Indeed, he received fierce criticism both from the conservative side, which viewed him as a dangerous socialist heretic, and from the left, which accused him of selling out to Yankee colonial and private sector interests (Jauretche 1984). Yet at no time did Prebisch demonstrate an aversion to private

²²Sotelsek Salem (2008) synthesizes the evolution of Prebisch's thought in three stages: ignorance, comprehension, and understanding and proposition.

²³In his work, Prebisch (1981, 292) shares his view of the synthesis between certain fundamental elements of socialism and economic liberalism. As regards socialism, he states: "Socialismo, en cuanto a destinar el excedente no de acuerdo a decisiones individuales sino a decisiones colectivas destinadas a elevar el ritmo de acumulación de capital y corregir progresivamente las diferencias estructurales de distribución del ingreso" [Socialism, insofar as the surplus is not allocated according to individual decisions but to collective decisions aimed at increasing the rate of capital accumulation and progressively correcting the structural differences in income distribution]. That is, he refers to planning the social use of surplus. As for economic liberalism, he argues that: "Y liberalismo económico en cuanto el ingreso así redistribuido podrá emplearse libremente en el mercado conforme a decisiones individuales; y también en cuanto las empresas podrán decidir por su propia determinación y en respuesta a ciertos incentivos, cómo responder mejor a la demanda de quienes gastan sus ingresos, asignando como deseen más conveniente el capital que les corresponde." [And economic liberalism insofar as the income thus redistributed may be freely used in the market in accordance with individual decisions; and also insofar as companies may decide by their own determination and in response to certain incentives, how best to respond to the demand of those who spend their income, allocating the capital that corresponds to them as they wish most conveniently].

property or initiatives, but rather to the private appropriation of surplus and the harmful consequences of concentrating the means of production (Prebisch 1981, 47).

In his writings, Prebisch firmly recognized the incompatibility between state ownership of the means of production and democratic values and human rights (Prebisch 1981, 32, 283). In his writings, Prebisch explored the potential tensions between extensive state ownership of the means of production and democratic values and human rights (Prebisch 1981, 32, 283). However, he did not categorically oppose all forms of state involvement in the economy. He acknowledged that public-private partnerships and some state enterprises, as seen in the USA or European countries, could coexist with democratic principles and human rights if managed effectively and transparently. Regarding ISI policies, he argued that they were a direct consequence of the adverse conditions imposed by the center on exports from the periphery (Prebisch, 1981). For Prebisch (1988), export substitution was not a technocratic invention but a response to the changing international conditions after the Second World War, especially following the generalization of bilateral trade agreements due to the disruption in international trade (Calcagno 2023).

Drawing on the UNCTAD *Trade and Development Report* (TDR) published in 2012, Rada (2014) clarifies Prebisch's position on tariffs and other policies to protect nascent industries. According to the author, in line with Prebisch (1959), the TDR reflects a certain skepticism towards devaluation as a policy to achieve competitiveness. Despite this, Prebisch defended protectionist measures in an attempt to gradually break poverty specialization and increase the productivity of the entire labor force in the medium term (Prebisch 1949, 1951, 1952).²⁴ Hence, to minimize the adverse effects of protectionism, it is essential to select the appropriate sectors of specialization (those with a certain comparative advantage, increasing returns to scale, the capacity to pull other sectors, etc.) and to identify their inefficiencies and disadvantages. Another key to success is the government's ability to reach a consensus on a national strategy that can garner the broadest possible support from society, trade unions, business associations, opposition parties, and other stakeholders. Prebisch also argued for the need to go beyond domestic markets to absorb both the industrial product and labor force supply. To this end, he proposed establishing bilateral agreements with other Latin American countries (periphery-periphery relations) for the trade of industrial goods.²⁵ None of these discussions are present in the articles analyzed here.

²⁴The concept of "poverty specialization" refers to the idea that certain economies, particularly those in developing countries, may become entrenched in producing low-value, primary goods or commodities that do not lead to significant economic development or diversification (Reinert 2018).

²⁵ Prebisch (1969) promoted the establishment of a common market for Latin America before the idea of creating a European common market.

As a result of the lessons learned over those years, Prebisch identified two changes in his position with respect to his previous assumptions. The first is related to his concern about increasing inequalities and the inability of economic growth to benefit the poorest (Prebisch 1983).²⁶ In the face of this evidence, he focused on the need to increase the rate of material capital accumulation or human resource formation through the productive employment of the poorest population at the expense of the privileged consumption of the high-income strata (Prebisch 1963). The second rethinking of his previous ideas is related to accelerated inflationary processes in most Latin American economies. None of these concerns appear in the articles that refer to Prebisch, nor is there any mention of how his thinking became more complex and incorporated significant nuances to his previous ideas.

Prebisch's work is much more varied, subtle, and profound than most of the articles that cite him would seem to suggest. Particularly striking is the lack of research that recovers and theoretically or empirically develops Prebisch's (1981) final attempt to formulate a global theory of development.

3. Discussion, conclusions and final reflections

This research aimed to analyze the current relevance of Prebisch's thought in articles published in development studies journals with the highest impact in JCR-ISI. Although a priori it might seem that his work is widely disseminated in development studies, my analysis of the number of references to the author in the selected period (139 references from 2010 to 2021) indicates that this is not the case. Almost all citations to Prebisch refer to the *Havana Manifesto* and are mostly found in only six journals. Most of the papers refer to him in an anecdotal way and ignore the depth of his thought and extensive work.²⁷ My results demonstrate a profound lack of knowledge of a key author in impact development journals. This is particularly true of the last period of his career

²⁶ In the words of Prebisch (1983, 1085): “[N]o había prestado atención suficiente al problema de las disparidades de ingreso. ... Tampoco había considerado con detenimiento, en los primeros años de la ECLAC, el hecho de que el crecimiento no había beneficiado a grandes masas de la población de ingresos bajos, mientras que en el otro extremo de la estructura social florecían los ingresos elevados. Es posible que esta actitud fuese un vestigio de mi anterior postura neoclásica, donde se suponía que el crecimiento económico corregiría por sí solo las grandes disparidades del ingreso a través de la acción de las fuerzas del mercado.” [I hadn't paid sufficient attention to the problem of income disparities. ... Nor had I, in the early years of ECLAC, given much thought to the fact that growth had not benefited large masses of the low-income population, while high incomes flourished at the other end of the social structure. This attitude may have been a vestige of my earlier neoclassical stance, where it was assumed that economic growth alone would correct large income disparities through the action of market forces].

²⁷ It is not fair to assume that because authors citing his work only make reference to one of his publications, or only in passing, that this reflects an anecdotal engagement with his work. While this might be true for the publication itself, Prebisch influence on those scholars – and their thinking for that publication – might of course be far more profound than there is space to develop or acknowledge in an article.

when he was appointed director of the *CEPAL Review* in 1973. At that time, Prebisch synthesized his ideas in *Capitalismo periférico: crisis y transformación* (1981, no English translation available).

The reasons Prebisch's ideas have been neglected point to several issues. Despite the markedly international scope of his work, only a very small portion is available in English.²⁸ The language barrier presents an additional challenge and further skews the analysis, as the journals selected for this review are in English. The high proportion (22%) of citations of Prebisch's article published in the *American Economic Review* (1959) mentioned in Table 2, in relation to the negligible proportion of his articles published only in Spanish is, to some extent, also a manifestation of this language bias. In the Anglo-Saxon sphere there is a persistent lack of attention to works in languages other than English despite their importance in constructing the history of development and underdevelopment.²⁹ Additionally, this phenomenon can be attributed to the evident disinterest of the economic orthodoxy in authors outside of Anglo-Saxon circles of scientific publication, which, in Prebisch's case, is referred to by Margulis (2017) as the "peripheralization of Prebisch" in *Global Political Economy*. However, this anglo-centrism should always be less prominent in the case of Prebisch, who, while working at the ECLAC and UNCTAD, provided intellectual leadership in international development during the 1950s and 1970s, and part of his work is available in English.

Furthermore, the passage of time can often lead to a simplification or distortion of an author's original contributions, as seen in the case of Smith, Marx, Keynes, and, as my results show, Prebisch. The tendency to depict Prebisch as a Marxist or an advocate of inward development policies, with an anti-export bias, reflects such caricatures. In the *History of Economic Ideas*, it is often difficult to identify an author's influences, and it is not clear to what extent these can be considered part of their intellectual legacy. In fact, even in those cases where Prebisch is cited out of context and seen as a Marxist related to Baran's version of the dependency theory, it is unclear

²⁸ Although his book *Capitalismo Periférico* was not translated, and neither were his complete works up to 1949, several of his articles published originally in *Revista de la CEPAL* which were his early reflections and formed the backbone for his book, were translated in *CEPAL Review* (the English version of the journal). See issues: number 1 (1976), 6 (1978), 7 (1979), 10 (1980) and 12 (1980).

²⁹ A clear example are the works of Daron Acemoglu and colleagues who study the history of colonization throughout Latin America without citing Spanish-language texts. Another earlier illustration of these biases is the survey article of the well-known and distinguished economist Nicholas Stern (Professor at LSE), who in his 90-page long article "The Economics of Development: A Survey", *Economic Journal*, 99 (397), 1989, pp. 597-685, practically ignores the contributions made by economists of the South to development studies, but Prebisch and A. K. Sen are mentioned. David Simon, who edited *Fifty Key Thinkers on Development* (Routledge, 2006) in the second edition of the book 2019 expanded considerable the number of development thinkers by mainly including authors from the South as he attempted to overcome their underrepresentation in the first edition.

that this should be regarded as part of his legacy. The ideas of ECLAC, structuralism, or dependency theory transcend those of Prebisch in particular, and vice versa, as the concepts proposed by Prebisch also extend beyond those developed by the school and its members. To explore these nuances in depth, future research should extend the timeline analyzed in my study (2010-2021) and incorporate primary sources to capture how Prebisch's ideas have evolved or been interpreted over the decades.

Lastly, some final reasons for the lack of attention to Prebisch's mature ideas, as synthesized in his book *Capitalismo Periférico*, can be attributed to two factors. The first relates to his support of pro-dependency views that were clearly critical of conventional development thinking. In 1981 work, he revisited the discussions in his years at ECLAC and delved into previously unresolved concerns, such as the generation of surplus in economies and its social use, capital accumulation with increasing labor force productivity, the hypertrophy of the state, or the ethical debates underlying different theoretical proposals (Prebisch 1981). In his final stage, Prebisch attempted to combine socialism and economic liberalism, but his theses were radical compared to those of the official development establishment. Examples of this are his appeals for the need to reduce consumption and the surplus of the privileged social strata, as well as his declarations on how social inequality is the root of centripetal capitalism for both the centers and the periphery. Although Prebisch attempted to formulate a global theory of development, none of these progresses of his thought are present in the development studies impact journals during the analyzed period. The second factor may stem from the perception that Prebisch's 1981 work is not sufficiently relevant. While it explores issues he had not previously analyzed in depth, it lacks clarity in proposing solutions to the challenges of peripheral capitalism (Hodara 1988). The ambiguity with which he refers to the synthesis between capitalism and socialism seems to rely on an improbable harmonization of social class interests, rendering his proposal politically unviable. This proposal should be interpreted more as a challenge rather than definitive solutions (Spagnolo, 1982). While recent literature in impact development journals not have extensively discussed his 1981 book, earlier works by authors like Hopenhayn (1982), Spagnolo (1982), Lira (1986), Di Filippo (1986), and Hodara (1988) indicate that his ideas were engaged with more deeply in the past.

As noted in the methodological section, measuring academic influence based on journal rankings and citation metrics, while providing valuable insights, obscures the true intellectual legacy of scholars like Raúl Prebisch and reflects an anglocentric bias that can limit the appreciation of

diverse scholarly contributions. Moreover, it is also important to acknowledge that some of the oversimplifications and omissions in the analysis of Prebisch's work could be a reflection of the broader academic practices and pressures in contemporary publishing, which can lead to superficial engagements with foundational ideas in development studies. Furthermore, the unquestioned faith in indexed scientific production as a marker of "excellence," alongside a commodification of knowledge circulation, restricts the diversity of intellectual contributions and silences the development of knowledge from other perspectives and contexts that do not conform to these narrow metrics.³⁰

Fortunately, although Prebisch's work is cited superficially and infrequently in mainstream development literature, his impact on the field cannot be reduced to citation counts or purely quantitative measures. The dissemination of knowledge reaches far beyond impact journals and despite that the academic obligations of scholars are now more focused on publishing in these journals, many researchers continue to recover in other formats (books, book chapters, biographies, grey literature etc.) the thought and history of the ideas of authors who are fundamental to development studies scholarship.³¹ For instance, Toye has written specifically about Prebisch (Toye and Toye 2003), but his paper does not appear in mainstream development journals. In recent years, there has been a series of studies on Prebisch's thought in its early phase, relevant for monetary issues and capital flows for peripheral countries (Sember 2018; CEPAL 2019; Pérez Caldentey and Vernengo 2019). In this regard, it is important to highlight two significant heterodox communities that have further developed Prebisch's center-periphery theory and consider his works (and ECLAC's more broadly) as direct sources of inspiration for their analyses of international asymmetries and domestic inequalities: the evolutionary and Post-Keynesian traditions.³² There has also been a growing body of literature published in English in the last decade that actively revisits discussions present in Prebisch's work, particularly regarding dependency theory (see, for example, Ahumada and Torres 2024; Kvangraven et al. 2017; Kvangraven 2021; Margulis 2017).

³⁰ For an analysis of these and other issues related to measurement metrics, see Feldman and Sandoval (2018), or López Castellano (2024), whose work on the Spanish case offers a broader perspective that integrates the incorporation of neoliberalism into the framework of academic evaluation.

³¹ It would have been beneficial to analyze the results including book chapters, books, and other formats. This broader scope might have provided a more accurate measure of Prebisch's influence in contemporary development studies.

³² One noteworthy element is the influence of Thirlwall's Law on growth models and its relationship to Prebisch's model (Dávila-Fernández and Amado 2015). A recent paper by Stockhammer (2022) highlights this synergy, positioning Prebisch as a crucial underpinning of a supply-side perspective that remains underdeveloped within Post-Keynesian discourse. Additionally, for insights into the connections with evolutionary literature, refer to Spinola (2022).

It is evident that Prebisch's work remains very much alive, as demonstrated by Edgar J. Dosman's magnificent biography on his figure (2010) or the project "Raúl Prebisch and Challenges of the 21st Century"; an initiative promoted by ECLAC since 2012.³³ Many of Prebisch's core ideas continue to influence development discourse, even when not explicitly attributed to him. For instance, any analysis that focuses on the asymmetries between developed and developing countries, whether framed as center-periphery or not, is inherently linked to Prebisch's pioneering work in this area. His lasting impact is also evident in Latin American debates and in the institutions he helped build, even if his contributions are not always immediately recognized. Future research should explore both the direct and subtle ways in which Prebisch's ideas continue to shape contemporary discussions on development studies.

Moreover, comparing Prebisch's influence with other pioneers of development studies like Dudley Seers and Celso Furtado using the same methodology could provide a more balanced view of his impact. It would also be valuable to explore whether this pattern holds for other authors (both conventional and non-conventional) or if it is particularly evident in their most significant works. Additionally, examining different types of journals, geographical areas, and fields of specialization could provide further insights into this phenomenon. Including international relations, globalization, and Area Studies journals, such as those focused on Latin American studies, might have uncovered more references to Prebisch, especially regarding his centre-periphery framework and work at UNCTAD, which inspired the New International Economic Order literature.³⁴

The "new" 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development of the United Nations is eminently focused on alleviating poverty without projecting structural views as did Prebisch. This agenda incorporates instrumental innovations, such as the development experimentalism of the Sveriges Riksbank Prize in Economic Sciences in Memory of Alfred Nobel 2024 Laureates Esther Duflo and Abhijit Banerjee, without addressing the original issues of development studies (López Castellano and García-Quero 2022). In the light these proposals for change, adopting an agenda focused on Prebisch's thought would require a structural approach to promote the social use of surplus as opposed to its private appropriation and the harmful consequences of the concentration of the means of production. It would also serve to put at the center of the development debate

³³ For more information, see: <https://biblioguias.cepal.org/portals/prebisch> It is also worth mentioning the "Raúl Prebisch Chair" inaugurated and promoted by ECLAC since 2001.

³⁴ Additionally, many relevant journals in the field of economic development were not considered, such as the Cambridge Journal of Economics, Structural Change and Economic Dynamics, Oxford Development Studies, and Industrial and Corporate Change. This highlights the need for a critical reflection on the possibly inadequate categorization of journals in the JCR when discussing the field of Development Studies.

topics such as industrialization, technological progress, the concentration of means of production, environmental challenges, and above all, the ethics of development. These themes addressed by Prebisch connect directly with original views of a structural nature (Immanuel Wallerstein, Erik Reinert, Carlota Pérez, Branko Milanovic, Marianna Mazucatto); with contemporary theoretical and political proposals such as the critical institutional political economy agenda (García-Quero and López Castellano 2022), the post globalization and reindustrialization (Cimoli 2023), the Green New Deal without growth (Mastini et al. 2022), a post-neoliberal development (Büscher et al. 2021) or the post-extractivist transitions (Gudynas 2023); and with research lines on ecologically unequal exchange, bioregions, or the history of development ideas.

To summarize and as a final conclusion, while it might seem subjective to categorize engagement with Prebisch's work as 'anecdotal' or 'deep', the relative scarcity of detailed discussions in high-impact journals does suggest a limited engagement with his theoretical depth. I hope that this article will contribute to some extent to recover and delve further into the thought of Raúl Prebisch and to revisit “the alternative Other Canon traditions” (Reinert et al. 2016) and “the old generation of development economists” (Meier 2001), what Krugman (1993) has called “high development theory.” A systemic view of his proposals is essential to address the contemporary challenges facing the discipline. It is also an antidote to magical thinking focused on micro and technical solutions that displaces from the agenda global ethical discussions on how to avoid the private appropriation of surplus and regulate its social use (Prebisch 1981).

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Appendix 1. Descriptive analysis of references to Raúl Prebisch in the period 1961–2021

All the graphs were created using the platform on the Scopus website. See: <https://www.scopus.com/search/form.uri?display=basic#basic>

2.1 Citations in different types of documents (1961–2021): 4,593 documents found. Total citations by year, type of document (article, book chapter, book, etc.), and subject area.

Documents by type

Articles (2,705), book chapters (801), books (668), reviews (302), conference papers (55), editorials (42), notes (16)

Documents by subject area

2.2 Citations in journals (1961–2021): 2,705 documents found.

Total number of documents by year, subject area, and country of principal authors.

Documents by year

Documents by subject area

Documents by country or territory

Compare the document counts for up to 15 countries/territories.

Appendix 2. Final references selected in each journal

Cambridge Journal of Regions Economy and Society	4
<p>Horner, R., Schindler, S., Haberly, D., & Aoyama, Y. (2018). Globalisation, uneven development and the North–South ‘big switch’. <i>Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society</i>, 11(1), 17-33.</p> <p>Andreoni, A., & Chang, H. J. (2017). Bringing production and employment back into development: Alice Amsden’s legacy for a new developmentalist agenda. <i>Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society</i>, 10(1), 173-187.</p> <p>Perez-Aleman, P., & Alves, F. C. (2017). Reinventing industrial policy at the frontier: catalysing learning and innovation in Brazil. <i>Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society</i>, 10(1), 151-171.</p> <p>Weller, S., & O’Neill, P. (2014). De-industrialisation, financialisation and Australia’s macro-economic trap. <i>Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society</i>, 7(3), 509-526.</p>	
World Development	14
<p>Romero, J. P., & Gramkow, C. (2021). Economic complexity and greenhouse gas emissions. <i>World Development</i>, 139 doi:10.1016/j.worlddev.2020.105317</p> <p>Irwin, D. A. (2021). The rise and fall of import substitution. <i>World Development</i>, 139 doi:10.1016/j.worlddev.2020.105306</p> <p>Jarrín-V, P., Falconí, F., Cango, P., & Ramos-Martin, J. (2021). Knowledge gaps in latin america and the caribbean and economic development. <i>World Development</i>, 146 doi:10.1016/j.worlddev.2021.105602</p> <p>Fukuda-Parr, S., Muchhala, B. (2020) The Southern origins of sustainable development goals: Ideas, actors, aspirations, <i>World Development</i>, 126: 104706,</p>	

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